

Migrant Worker Policy Recommendations

for decent living and working
conditions for migrant workers
employed in agriculture in Canada

Audience: Federal and Provincial Governments of Canada

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Project Information

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SECTION I Introduction

I. Objectives, Methodology, and Participants

1. Research Objectives and Significance

The project investigates the struggles for fundamental rights of Migrant Agricultural Workers (MAWs) and of their allies and networks of supporters in Canada and Italy, with the central question: “How the material and symbolic boundaries of ci-

tizenship are challenged, produced, and reproduced by an essential yet structurally marginalized workforce?” The research focused on the agency and mobilizations of MAWs and their networks, as well as on what facilitates and hinders claim-making and bottom-up mobilization for the recognition of rights.

2. Methodological and Analytical Framework (Synthesis Map)

Study Element	Italy Context	Canada Context
Research Duration	2022 (October) – 2025 (November)	2022 (April) – 2024 (November)
Primary Methodology	Extended Ethnography (PAR)	Situational Analysis (SA)
Additional Components	Media Scan + Policy Analysis (Legal Status)	Media Scan + Policy Analysis (Legal Status)
Ethnography (Duration/Scope)	5 months of fieldwork (Year 2025). Over 500 MAWs met.	Focus on consultative meetings, participant observations and organized networks
Interviews & Meetings	48 Interviews + 14 Consultative Meetings 13 women (4 MAWs)	12 Interviews + 9 Consultative Meetings
Fieldwork Engagement	Meals Distribution, Night Outreach, Low-threshold contact with the homeless; Street Union	Migrant Organizations/Allies
Reference Population	Coverage of 5 regions: Piedmont, Puglia, Sicily, Basilicata, Campania, Lombardy	Migrant-Led Organizations. Coverage of 4 provinces: Nova Scotia, Ontario, Quebec, British Columbia

II. Methodology and Structural Context

Research Focus and Framework

This study is based on a comparative analysis of MAWs’ struggles in Italy and Canada. The research utilized an Extended Ethnography and Participatory Action Research (PAR) in the Italian context, while adopting Situational Analysis (SA) complemented by consultation with organized networks in the Canadian context. This methodology allowed the research to focus on the agency and mobilizations of MAWs and their networks, highlighting what facilitates and hinders claim-making and bottom-up mobilization for rights recognition.

Structural Critique (Canada Preeminence)

For both contexts, exploitation is reinforced by precarious legal status, control and discipline through housing, spatial and social isolation. Housing together with legal status, in particular, emerge as

central to collective self-organization, shaping both opportunities and constraints. In Canada, the direct tie between a migrant’s legal status and their employer, established through the Seasonal Agricultural Worker Program (SAWP), is identified as a primary enabling factor for exploitation. This status-employer link creates a “breeding ground for contemporary forms of slavery,” facilitating the complete subordination of workers.

Nature of Struggles and Barriers

In Italy, struggles are typically fragmented micro-struggles focused on survival - we have called them “struggles for humanity” - , and action is hindered by ideological fragmentation among allies. In Canada, the research found evidence of advanced and organized mobilization led by cohesive networks. These struggles are clearly focused on legal status, interpreted as the “right to have ri-

ghts.” However, the main barrier remains legal precarity, which generates a profound fear of reprisal and deportation—a powerful deterrent against collective action. The drivers of agency in Canada are identified as cohesion and a well-defined interpretive framework (framing), supported by allied organizations that operate as a united migrant-led front.

III. Conclusions and Central Political Message Co-Constructed Policy Mandate

These recommendations are the result of three years of research and, crucially, a co-construction process involving three specific consultative meetings with research participants. They are an invitation to continue building and solidifying alliances based on years of activism, trade union work, and international connections.

Central Message and Call to Action

The key message of this work is that the success or failure of MAWs’ struggles in both contexts hinges on the ecosystem of allies and network of supporters—specifically, their cohesion, strategy, and whether they are migrant-led.

The recommendations are intended as living material to be used by activists, associations, trade unions, and, above all, MAWs themselves, as a tool for possible change and transformation. They are designed to support MAWs in their long-term struggle for just living and working conditions and, most importantly, to ensure that the dignity of their lives and their rights is central to every single, collective, and political action.

This research calls for the implementation of policies, practices, and solidarity actions with an intersectional and decolonial approach. It highlights the need for a holistic and integrated approach that involves communities from the local to the national level, where every actor assumes responsibility for the care and protection of people and rights.

Local actors (institutions, unions, associations, and workers) are encouraged to jointly define a realistic timeline and shared priorities for each recommendation, basing their implementation on the specific resources available in each context.

Alignment with Global Objectives

The recommendations directly reference the following 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including; Goal 3: Good Health and Well-Being; Goal 4: Quality Education; Goal 5: Gender Equality; Goal 8: Decent Work and Economic

Growth (in particular point 8.7: effective measures to eradicate forced labour, modern slavery, and human trafficking).

Document’s Structure

Following this introductory section, the second section contains the Executive Summary – the recommendations in brief. The third section includes the recommendations designated for Federal and Provincial Governments and State Institutions.

Quotes are excerpts from research interviews conducted in Canada with former migrant workers, activists, and academics. To maintain anonymity, participants are identified by codes based on their profile (A: Activist; A_MAW: Migrant Agricultural Worker and Activist; CA: Canada).

SECTION II

Executive Summary: Urgent Reforms for Migrant Agricultural Workers' Rights

Nr.	Recommendation	High-Impact Message
1	Reform Temporary Foreign Worker Programs to Ensure Open, Secure Legal Status and Enhanced Protections	Untie status from employer: Grant Permanent Residency upon arrival and Open Work Authorizations to dismantle systemic exploitation.
2	Make Difficult (Agricultural) Work Decent/Competitive	Dignify farm work: Fund the agricultural sector to ensure working and living conditions are decent, attractive, and competitive with other industries.
3	Mechanisms to Guarantee the Right to Unionize and Bargain Collectively	Amend provincial labour legislations to explicitly grant agricultural workers the same rights to freedom of association, unionization, and collective bargaining as in other sectors.
4	Establish Accessible and Safe Channels for Reporting Abuse	Report without fear: Develop and publicize confidential, multilingual reporting channels that guarantee full protection from retaliation and deportation.
5	Strengthen Agricultural Recruitment-/ Employment Inspection/ Enforcement	Addressing substandard agricultural conditions requires a shift toward proactive provincial monitoring and enforcement, supported by federal intervention to direct labour toward jurisdictions that uphold rigorous human rights standards
6	Promote Decent Agricultural Work	To transform industry standards, the government should introduce a monitored rights-based labelling system that leverages consumer pressure, ethical sourcing mandates, and public awareness to eliminate systemic labour abuse
7	Access to Basic Services for All (Agricultural) Migrant Workers	Governments must implement a government-led, ethical recruitment and placement system while guaranteeing universal, status-blind access to healthcare—with a focus on reproductive rights—and investing in community support and professional training to ensure long-term stability for migrant workers
8	Establish Formal Consultation Mechanisms with Migrant Agricultural Workers	Incorporate lived experience: Institute formal and regular consultation processes that directly involve migrant workers and their representatives in policy design.
9	Invest in and Support Research with/for Migrant Agricultural Workers' Conditions and Policy Impact	Ensure evidence-based change: Provide consistent and robust funding for research to inform policymaking, track effectiveness, and understand evolving needs.

SECTION III

Migrant Worker Policy Recommendations - Federal and Provincial governments of Canada

The governments at all levels have an obligation to ensure that the agricultural system on which Canadians rely on is **healthy, sustainable, and just**. To dismantle an employment regime consistently described as generating structural and systematic exploitation and giving rise to forms of **modern slavery**¹, while the Federal government must urgently overhaul the existing legal and regulatory immigration frameworks governing a key aspect of the labour supply to the agricultural sector, the provincial governments must also raise the bar in terms of holding the agricultural employers to modern decent work and housing standards. This urgency is heightened by the existence of a persistent **'exceptionalism'**² concerning the monitoring and enforcement of agricultural workers' rights. **Provincial governments** must immediately reform labour laws to include agricultural workers, who are currently excluded from key protections of Employment Standards, Health and Safety, Work, Housing and Labour Relations legislations. This fundamental inclusion is necessary for effective inspection and enforcement and to ensure decent working and living conditions.

This being said, this can only be achieved through genuinely participatory and democratic consultative processes in policy formulation.

Recommendation 1. Reform Temporary Foreign Worker Programs to Ensure Open, Secure Legal Status and Enhanced Protections

Canada must undertake a comprehensive reform of its temporary foreign worker programs, starting with the **Seasonal Agricultural Worker Program (SAWP)**. The current measures to tie a worker's legal status to a specific employer/group of employers is a critical and legally problematic issue, as unanimously highlighted through this research, prior studies³ and international organizations/experts⁴. This fundamental change is crucial to eliminate the inherent vulnerability caused by employer-tied permits, empowering workers to leave abusive situations without fear of losing the right to work and without the fear of deportation - and significantly improving their access to rights. This fundamental shift can be achieved through **two urgent and immediate changes**, as evidenced by various studies⁵, including those shared wi-

1 United Nations, Report of the Special Rapporteur on Contemporary Forms of Slavery, Including Its Causes and Consequences, by Tomoya Obokata United Nations, 2024

2 Basok, T., Tucker, E. M., Vosko, L. F., Caxaj, C. S., Hennebry, J. L., Mayell, S., ... & Weiler, A. M. (2025). The 'contract' and its discontents: Can it address protection gaps for migrant agricultural workers in Canada? *International Migration*, 63(1), e13121; Vosko, L. F., Tucker, E., & Casey, R. (2019). Enforcing employment standards for temporary migrant agricultural workers in Ontario, Canada: Exposing underexplored layers of vulnerability. *International Journal of Comparative Labour Law and Industrial Relations*, 35(2);

3 Patterson, D. (2025). *Realities of Precarity in Canada's Seasonal Fields: Struggles, Advocacy, and Restricted Spaces and Voices* (Doctoral dissertation, Université d'Ottawa/University of Ottawa). Patterson, D. (2025). *Realities of Precarity in Canada's Seasonal Fields: Struggles, Advocacy, and Restricted Spaces and Voices* (Doctoral dissertation, Université d'Ottawa/University of Ottawa); Weiler, A. M., & McLaughlin, J. (2019). Listening to migrant workers: should Canada's Seasonal Agricultural Worker Program be abolished?. *Dialectical Anthropology*, 43(4), 381-388; Depatie-Pelletier, E., & Dumont Robillard, M. (2013). Interdiction de changer d'employeur pour les travailleurs migrants: obstacle majeur à l'exercice des droits humains au Canada. *Revue québécoise de droit international*, 26(2), 163-200.

4 United Nations, Report of the Special Rapporteur on Contemporary Forms of Slavery, Including Its Causes and Consequences, by Tomoya Obokata United Nations, 2024 <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/g24/120/97/pdf/g2412097.pdf>.

5 Amnesty International. (2025). "Canada has destroyed me." *Labour exploitation of migrant workers in Canada*. Amnesty International Ltd. from https://amnesty.ca/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/AMR_20_8872_2025-EN.pdf

thin the CIMM⁶ and SOCI⁷ standing committees:

Grant Permanent Residency Status upon Arrival: Guarantee migrant workers a *permanent residency status* upon arrival. This foundational change ensures workers are recognized as full residents and ensures full access to rights, including the fundamental rights to leave and re-enter the country and to access justice and reparation in case of a right violation.

Issue Open and Decoupled Work Authorizations: Change the system to untie the work authorizations from *any* specific employer or group of employers, work location, occupation, placement agent and/or sector, while their permanent status application is being processed. This is critical to eliminating the power imbalance inherent in tied permits, allowing workers the essential freedom to leave abusive situations and fully access all fundamental and labour rights, as confirmed by research and advocacy networks⁸.

“They have jobs, their kids went to school, they did everything, but they lacked the status which had such profound impacts on their lives... Albeit legally, they were temporary foreign workers, but still had many of the same challenges that undocumented farm workers had.” (I_5_2024_A_CA).

“Canada consistently... have programs that dehumanize and exploit people... We are denied basic things. The laws that are designed to protect workers in Canada, migrant workers are excluded from those laws... That is why the UN rapporteur accurately described it as a breeding ground. You’re tied to the employer and at the same time denied basic human rights and excluded from basic labour protection.” (I_6_2024_A_MAW_CA)

While the above reforms are being adopted and implemented, the interpretation and application of the current regulations for the **Open Work Permit for Vulnerable Workers** (widely criticized for being inadequate and are often described as me-

6 Standing Committee on Citizenship and Immigration. <https://www.ourcommons.ca/Committees/en/CIMM?parl=44&session=1>

7 Social Affairs, Sciences and Technology standing committee. <https://sencanada.ca/en/committees/SOCI/45-1>

8 Association for the rights of Household and farm workers; Migrant Rights Network; Justice for Migrant Workers

chanisms that lead to further **revictimization**⁹, exclusion, and a pathway to becoming undocumented) must be significantly broadened to ensure a maximum eligibility and streamlining of the application process.

“Yeah, we’ve had lots of individuals have difficulty finding work either with an open work permit for vulnerable workers, so sometimes people have gone out of town and have been able to get work” (I_10_2024_A_CA).

Recommendation 2. Make Difficult (Agricultural) Work Decent/Competitive

It is imperative to significantly enhance the institutional support and special multi-year financial packages for the agricultural sector targeting employers, municipalities and provincial governments, to ensure that working and living conditions on agricultural farms not only become decent and equivalent to other sectors and industries, but in fact become attractive to both local and (im)migrant workers, and even competitive with special programs facilitating access to decent family housing rent and ownership, access to motorized vehicles, access to land ownership, access to rural daycare services, etc. as well as radical financial bonus in case of temporary dangerous task assignments, longer work schedules or regions remote from basic social services offer.

In particular, there is an urgent need to modernize the access to Employment Insurance benefits. It is imperative for the federal government to significantly enhance the Employment Insurance System to ensure that working on agricultural farms is an option that always makes financial sense both for local workers and newcomers in the

country.

Federal and provincial governments should start by collaborating to ensure that employment, health, safety and housing¹⁰ STANDARDS are specifically tailored to the unique risks of agricultural work, including access to potable water, protection from extreme weather, safe transportation, and facilities and equipment for training on pesticide handling and machinery operation, provided in languages understood by the agricultural work candidates¹¹.

The **PROVINCIAL** governments must undertake a comprehensive review and reform of all provincial labour regulations that govern the agricultural sector, in addition to the not only workers’ legal residency status - (as addressed in Recommendation 1/federal immigration law), i.e. but **also all provincial employment standards, occupational health and safety (OHS) provisions**¹², and specific sector-related regulations such as industrial housing regulations. This agricultural reform must introduce transparent and monitorable public standards, including standards for job placement services by private agents and agencies.

1. Workplace injuries compensation - for them and their families, as required by law¹³.
2. Housing standards: The **Federal Government must urgently establish and enforce mandatory housing standards** for Migrant Agricultural Workers (MAWs).

Recommendation 3. Mechanisms to Guarantee the Right to Unionize and Bargain Collectively

Amend provincial labour legislations to explicitly grant agricultural workers the same rights to fre-

9 Basok, T., Tucker, E. M., Vosko, L. F., Caxaj, C. S., Hennebry, J. L., Mayell, S., ... & Weiler, A. M. (2025). The ‘contract’ and its discontents: Can it address protection gaps for migrant agricultural workers in Canada?. *International Migration*, 63(1), e13121

10 Please see also: Caxaj, C. S., Weiler, A. M., & Martyniuk, J. (2024). Housing conditions and health implications for migrant agricultural workers in Canada: A scoping review. *Canadian Journal of Nursing Research*, 56(1), 16–28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08445621231203086>

11 Caxaj, C. S., George, G., Lozanski, K., & Mayell, S. (2025). Cultural Safety in Service Provision for Migrant Agricultural Workers? An Empirical Exploration: Caxaj et al. *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 1-24.

12 Mayell, S., McLaughlin, J., Hennebry, J., Sanchez, G. V., Goswami, P., & Hanley, J. (2025). The point of no return? Impediments to return to work for injured migrant agricultural workers in two Canadian provinces. *New Solutions: A Journal of Environmental and Occupational Health Policy*, (1):32. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10482911251314149>

13 Mayell, S., McLaughlin, J., Hennebry, J., Sanchez, G. V., Goswami, P., & Hanley, J. (2025). The point of no return? Impediments to return to work for injured migrant agricultural workers in two Canadian provinces. *New Solutions: A Journal of Environmental and Occupational Health Policy*, (1):32. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10482911251314149>

edom of association, unionization, and collective bargaining as in other sectors. This right is a fundamental human right enshrined in multiple international labour conventions ratified by Canada. This includes removing legal barriers that prevent their inclusion in existing unions and ensuring fairer power relations by protecting workers from employers' retaliation for organizing. This guarantees a crucial mechanism for workers to collectively address issues such as low wages, poor working conditions, and exploitation¹⁴.

The Federal Government must immediately inform Migrant Agricultural Workers (MAWs) of their constitutionally protected right to join a union in Canada. This is the critical first step toward quickly improving their well-being and addressing systemic issues.

Union representation, secured by a collective agreement, is a proven mechanism for swiftly resolving many of the challenges faced by MAWs, as demonstrated by the thousands of migrant workers currently represented by UFCW (United Food

and Commercial Workers).

"we're besides working with different unions yeah, the workers that I work with are not able to unionize which is why it's so important that we build or we have the infrastructure for them to have sort of associations if you will [...] they would be able to speak about those labour rights, farm by farm or conglomerate by conglomerate as it is." (I_10_2024_A_CA)

Recommendation 4. Establish Accessible and Safe Channels for Reporting Abuse

The federal/provincial governments must immediately develop and widely publicize confidential, multilingual, and easily accessible reporting mechanisms for migrant workers to report immigration/labour exploitation, abuse, and violations of their rights. These channels must explicitly guarantee protection from retaliation, including employer reprisal or deportation, to encourage reporting without fear.

14 Gabriel, C., & Macdonald, L. (2025). Transnational Activism and Temporary Agricultural Workers in Canada During the COVID-19 Pandemic. In *Transnational Activism in North America* (pp. 127-152). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland; UFCW and the Agricultural Worker Alliance. (2023). The status of migrant agricultural workers in Canada. Accessed 3 November 2025.

Recommendation 5. Strengthen Agricultural Recruitment-Employment Inspection/Enforcement

It is imperative for provincial governments to significantly enhance the systems for inspecting and monitoring placement, working and living conditions on agricultural farms. This includes increasing resources for labour inspectors, implementing unannounced inspections, and imposing severe penalties for employers and recruiters who violate labour laws and human rights.

"Inspections have been reactionary in nature instead of proactive... We continue to have people that are living in, you know, terrible living conditions and terrible working conditions that are unsafe, that are violations of human rights... the continued discussion is whose obligation or responsibility is it to address that?" (I_10_2024_A_CA).

The exclusion of agricultural workers from basic labour and housing standards constitutes a strong call, **given the federal nature of these programs**, for the Federal Government to step in and take strong leadership on this matter - such as prioritising worker job placement in provinces with labour legislations efficient in the prevention of agricultural workers' rights violation.

Recommendation 6. Promote decent agricultural work

Beyond legislative reform designed to promote decent agricultural work, the Canadian government should simultaneously introduce concrete, collaborative measures to raise industry standards. Specifically, it should develop and implement a certification system for workers' rights, alongside existing standards for product quality and environmental impact. This system must be designed in collaboration with civil society organizations, ethical employers, and entities directly involved in agricultural production. It should feature continuous monitoring and a comprehensive mechanism of:

Incentives for producers who achieve a "zero exploitation" label.

Penalties/lack of opportunities for those who fail to meet minimum regulatory requirements. This approach recognizes and rewards virtuous practices while discouraging systemic abuse. This type of mechanism is supported by international research on the role of ethical certification in the US and Canadian agricultural sectors¹⁵.

Launch National Public Awareness Campaigns on Migrant Workers' Rights. Initiate and fund comprehensive public education awareness campaigns aimed at educating the broader Canadian public, at all levels of education, about the fundamental rights of migrant agricultural workers and the systemic issues they face. These campaigns should highlight not only the workers' essential contribution to the food system but also the importance of ethical labour practices and dignified working and living conditions.

Implement Ethical Sourcing and Fair Labour Practices within Agricultural Supply Chains. Develop and enforce public policies that encourage or mandate ethical sourcing practices within the agricultural sector, potentially through consumer pressure mechanisms or certification programs that ensure fair treatment and conditions for workers throughout the supply chain. This incentivizes large players to support farms adhering to high labour standards.

Recommendation 7. Access to Basic Services for All (Agricultural) Migrant Workers

Ensure public International Recruitment and Sponsorship Services: It is imperative to ensure bilateral two-government management to offer free and unbiased recruitment services for agricultural jobs in Canada, including access for sponsored candidates to a micro-credit program/cash advances available in the country of origin.

Ensure Free and Unbiased Ag Job Placement Services: It is imperative to ensure institutional management of free and unbiased placement services in agricultural jobs, including access for candidates to a micro-credit program/cash advances and access to efficient collective transportation systems towards all Canadian rural areas.

15 Borrelli, E. (2025). Certifying Justice? Migrant Farmworker Precarity and the Role of Ethical Certification in US and Canadian Agriculture (Doctoral dissertation, University of Windsor (Canada); Borrelli, E., & Olinto, B. (2022). Migrant Labour in the Agrifood Sector, Ethical Food Label and Certification Schemes: A Literature Review; Caxaj, C. S., Shkopi, E., Naranjo, C. T., Chew, A., Hao, Y. T., & Nguyen, M. (2023b). Health, social and legal supports for migrant agricultural workers in France, Italy, Spain, Germany, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand: A scoping review. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11, E01-E11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1182816>

Access to urgent care for (injured) migrant workers: Federal and provincial governments must take all urgent and necessary measures to guarantee continuous access to care for (injured) migrant workers, regardless of their employment or legal status

Prioritizing Women’s Reproductive Health: Current barriers prevent women, especially those with unstable legal status, from accessing essential reproductive health services, such as pregnancy termination¹⁶. Furthermore, a general lack of available family doctors and healthcare providers creates significant access challenges even for women with established legal status.

Guarantee Universal and Equitable Access to Reproductive Healthcare: Mandate that all women, regardless of their legal or immigration status, are guaranteed immediate, comprehensive access to all necessary reproductive health services, including pregnancy termination, without fear of documentation or legal repercussions.

Strengthen Primary Care Provider Capacity: Invest in programs to recruit, train, and retain family doctors and primary care providers in underserved areas to ensure that all residents, including women with precarious legal status, can secure a regular healthcare provider quickly and easily.

Establish Dedicated Navigation Pathways: Create dedicated, confidential health navigation services to assist women facing access barriers—particularly those with unstable status—in locating and securing appointments for specialized reproductive health needs. Furthermore, all factors that create and maintain dependence on employers to access healthcare must be removed, and free access to language translation must be ensured.

“So we are so careful... about eating food that is not good for the body, without pesticides, but we still have to work on awareness related to workers’ rights... There is a lot of work still to do there.” (I_6_2024_A_CA).

Invest in Major Community Welcoming and Support Programs: The programs (related to the agricultural sector and beyond) funding community organizations offering services to migrant

workers upon arrival in the country, and during their stay until permanent status is recognized, are key and should be vastly expanded - in particular in rural areas.

Invest in Major Apprenticeship and Professional Training Programs: (related to the agricultural sector and beyond) which are accessible to migrant workers following the conclusion of their seasonal employment, serving as a pathway to long-term occupational stability and combating irregularity.

Recommendation 8. Establish Formal Consultation Mechanisms with Migrant Agricultural Workers

Institute formal and regular consultation processes where government bodies – Federal and Provincial - engage directly with migrant agricultural workers and their representatives and support/advocacy organizations when developing, reviewing, or implementing policies that affect seasonal/temporary migrant agricultural workers. This ensures that policy decisions are informed by direct experience and expertise from the ground. To this goal, the Federal government must allocate dedicated funding and provide institutional support for grassroots, worker-led organizations that directly represent and advocate for migrant agricultural workers. Recognizing these groups as essential partners ensures that policy development and implementation are informed by the lived experiences and priorities of the workers themselves.

Recommendation 9. Invest in and Support Research with/for Migrant Agricultural Workers’ Conditions and Policy Impact

Provide consistent and robust funding for academic and community-based research on the conditions of migrant agricultural workers, the effectiveness of current policies, and the impacts of proposed reforms. This ensures evidence-based policymaking and a deeper understanding of the challenges and needs.

16 Canadian Women’s Foundation. (2024). Women and gender-diverse migrant workers in rural Canada: Research snapshot. Canadian Women’s Foundation. Accessed 3 November 2025, from <https://canadianwomen.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Issues-Affecting-Precarious-Status-Migrant-Workers-Research-Snapshot.pdf>; Cohen, A., & Caxaj, S. (2018). Bodies and borders: Migrant women farmworkers and the struggle for sexual and reproductive justice in British Columbia, Canada. *Alternate Routes: A Journal of Critical Social Research*, 29, 90 – 117, <https://alternateroutes.ca/index.php/ar/article/view/22448>

Co-authorship and Special thanks

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I also wish to thank each and every one of the participants in this international study, as well as my Canadian supervisor, Dr. Susana Caxaj, and Italian supervisor at Ca' Foscari University of Venice, Professor Perocco, for their precious comments and invaluable feedback on the initial drafts of this document. Furthermore, I wish to express my profound gratitude to the CERC (Canada Excellence Research Chair in Migration and Integration) and Professor Anna Triandafyllidou for their kind hospitality during the fieldwork, and to Professor Donatella Della Porta for her support during the secondment at the COSMOS (Centre on Social Movement Studies) in Florence.

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Appendix:

Programme poster for the Recommendations launch - 27.11.2025

Ca' Foscari
University
of Venice
Department of
Philosophy and
Cultural Heritage

November 27th 2025
10.00 AM – 12.00 PM EST
(Toronto) / 4.00 PM –
6.00 PM CET (Rome)

[Link Zoom](#)

Marie Skłodowska-Curie
Project: Migrants' protests:
how the borders of citizenship
are conceived, mobilized and
constructed by migrants' farm
workers protest

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agreement No. 101066659

Migrant Worker Policy Recommendations Launch

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(DTMF), Canada

Santiago Escobar

United Food and Commercial Workers Union Canada

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